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MESS 0013

MIMS 2.83→2.2.5.3: The crossing of POS Theory and time as a subset of
Change Theory

Sf. R. Careaga, BSEE, MSTOM
October 2022

ABSTRACT

In a recent episode of The Pulse, Jonathan Kines and the author discussed the mimsy of control, the Changes in our society, and a myriad of topics. One of these was a proposal of the initial mimsy for a POS/Change Theory crossing junction, which might suffice to explain present decay. In this paper the author discusses decay and life cycles very broadly; and it is hoped a new MIMS may eventually birth through this uniting point, though the hypothesis title and purpose is not clear to the author, yet.

Keywords: MIMS - philosophy - POS theory - Changes - society - empires - collapse - decay rate

POS Theory as a depiction of the decay rate

Ayn Rand's depiction of the process by which looters, moochers, and mystics ruined the works of greater minds, scientific and industrious men, was that it had to do with the ceding of authority, and the disinterest of the public, as well as subsequent generations, to care as much as their antecedents¹. This is typified by welfarism, thievery, lying (or stealing credit), among myriad social disorders (Useful Idiots², "Stupid Kids,"³ and SJWs⁴ come to mind), coming almost exclusively from the least productive 93-97% of society. These 'simps' rely upon persons of higher moral and ethical fiber, not to mention work ethic, know-how, bravado, and various other masculine features.

What if, however, as we observe the fruition of her's, Orwell's, and Huxley's predictions finally coming to pass in the 21st century, which has more to do with specific decay rates built into the Changes?

Consider the potentiality of this issue, discussed in terms of Imperial decay, which averages around 250 years⁵. One would ask how certain dynasties lasted longer, or why shorter. One would ask if there were natural forces at work to ensure that no one family, lineage, or nation-state was capable of dominating forever.

One would naturally compare the life cycle of these to those in natural living organisms. The author is not presupposing that we can know the *exact* decay rate. But perhaps we at least take the time to observe the connection between the birth and growth (and flowering) of nations as great as the United States of America, or the Roman Empire, and their geniuses, and the ease with which they can operate versus the regulatory morass created by lazy, stupid government workers, politicians, and POS supremes who want to destroy rather than build a nation. Ie - "the Axis & Sons"⁶ and the New World Order⁷.

For example, the United States achieved the "Royal Sway" in 1945. By 1952 it had the Hydrogen Bomb⁸, which was almost immediately stolen by the USSR, ensuring the Cold War. By 1963 JFK was killed by the CIA/SS⁹ - perhaps a Nazi operation (PAPERCLIP¹⁰) - and yes although Civil Rights was passed in 1964, and we went to the moon in '69, the Vietnam War was dragging everything down. Pretty soon the anti-family, Malthusian, Kissinger and the Trilateral Commission were laying the groundwork for world shrinkage and the destruction of classical liberalism. By the 1980s, even as the culture itself crescendoed, the President (Reagan) was an actor, answering to CEOs¹¹, and he had Alzheimer's as well. Then the POTUS was taken over by the CIA chief, whose father was a bonified Nazi. Then the Clinton Crime Syndicate, and Project for a New American Century, Skull & Bones, and well, we see now the power the CIA and Deep State wield to attack any POTUS that tries to be independent. And we are back to a POTUS with Alzheimer's.

Furthermore, the culture has stagnated, and music, arts, and much else (other than technology) remains in a state of early decay. The freight trains and highway infrastructure remain very 1950s-60s design, and Television still holds a massive sway over the minds of people from that era as they get older. Their bulge

¹ <https://aynrand.org/novels/atlas-shrugged/>

² [YouTube Stages of communist takeovers- Yuri Bezmenov \(Leftists are useful IDIOTS\)](#)

³ https://www.academia.edu/87490521/MESS0006_The_POS_Wave_continues_because_Agenda

⁴ [YouTube Kanye West SLAMS Black Lives Matter Calling It A SCAM, Says ITS OVER And The Polls PROVE HIM RIGHT](#)

⁵ <https://www.times-standard.com/2017/06/28/the-average-age-of-an-empire-a-mere-250-years/>

⁶ Ibid. pp. 3

⁷ https://www.academia.edu/51022722/Winning_the_New_Cold_War_World_War_3

⁸ <https://www.britannica.com/technology/thermonuclear-bomb>

⁹ George Hickey fired the most crucial killing blow, regardless how many stood on the grassy knoll or who fired shots from the library. He was NOT a SS agent, not really. Who, at age 40, suddenly becomes an agent working on the detail of the POTUS, and then carries the only frangible rifle round in the motorcade?

<https://www.amazon.com/Mortal-Error-Shot-That-Killed/dp/149095242X>

¹⁰ <https://documents2.theblackvault.com/documents/fbifiles/operationpaperclip-fbi1.pdf>

¹¹ [YouTube former Merrill Lynch CEO Don Regan tells Ronald Reagan to speed it up](#)

in birth-signal is not yet totally passed, but the effect upon the decay rate of the USA® appears to be both economic stagflation (perhaps hyperinflation if the NWO has its way), as well as moral confusion and familial destruction. The current POTUS is a daughter-raping¹² POS Supreme who admitted to rigging an election¹³, and is clearly under the control of China, or worse. The effect, therefore, of the decay is to give the appearance that the US is doomed as an empire to within a short distance from this [current year]. Most do not expect the country to make it [as it was designed] to its 300th year. Some openly talk of secessions (CA/TX) and Civil War. But why should this be so? Everything changes, but why should the looters, moochers, and POS Wave continue and take over the system? Is the general apathy of the populace fatigue post-COVID, or part of a natural decay rate, related to the Changes?

Time as a passage of events, marked by mental cognizance

It's important to understand that the EPEMC expresses time not as a proper dimension, though it is certainly a mathematical one, but as the marking by the mind or "Critical Observer" of the changes of atomic Mass-Energy (ME). These *events* are recorded in memory and memetic systems, imperfectly, and with great backwards and forwards lossiness - as has been stated elsewhere. Nevertheless, the passage of streams of data through an *annulus of observation*, as per Triple-Plane Theory¹⁴ (TPT) suggests that time is very relevant as a recording and calculation MIMS, but not the central cause.

In another paper, the author will discuss the "bolus" effect - called Aether Flexion Wave¹⁵ - in its relation to the sudden coming and going of the apparent passage of time and events, in packets or cloisters of events. However, suffice it to say in this paper, the AFW is expressed purely as a construct of the Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis¹⁶ (CRH), which stipulates that:

- ★ All Change is merely the rearrangement of charge data - dæther - according to Causality's 'black box' equation of 1) curl, 2) gradient, 3) potential, 4) LRC¹⁷, and 5) permittivity data in the charge field, or flux vortex//matrix.
 - The description of these, visually, is found in the Dougherty Set.¹⁸

This implies that birth, life, and the whole life-cycle, including decay rate is related to this phenomenon of CRH. Those things, come, rise, and go/decline... even disappear and are re-constituted, according to descriptions of these above features, in a complex, non-linear equation.

¹²

<https://www.msn.com/en-us/news/politics/alleged-showers-with-my-dad-president-joe-biden-s-daughter-reportedly-writes-of-alleged-abuse-in-diary/ar-AAAYCrGi>

¹³ Joe Biden says he's built most extensive "voter fraud" org in history

¹⁴ https://www.academia.edu/86922819/Structure_of_the_Uni_Multiverse_pre_EPEMC

¹⁵ <https://bit.ly/3BXLwZm> MESS0012: CRH - The Aether Flexion Wave

¹⁶ https://www.academia.edu/72712073/Cosmic_Rearrangement_Hypothesis

¹⁷ Inductance, resistance, capacitance - ie Kirchoff's circuit theories in a short-term.

¹⁸ The Dougherty Set (playlist)

Figure 1 - a *proposed* arrangement¹⁹ of the 5 features of PEMF, for future mimsy; credit: author

Change Theory, Life-cycles, and the inevitable ‘gravity’ of *Falling*.

The downfall of the gods - of the Heracleian figure and of the Fertility God-star - and their ruin is one of the stories that mankind cannot be shed of. Why would it, considering the effect that the appearance of gravity (as a separate force) has on all things. However, as discussed in another MESSy, it is quite possible that gravity is a mere contraction of calculations (by Causality) in a polar relationship between one subset of principles (*P* power) of the Law of Resonance with those in its compatriot on the “X”: the Law of Conservation. Mimsically, the former is in the region between Wood and Fire, or the Law of Polarity and that of Causation. However, this appears to be mostly a relation of the Wood-Fire-Metal tri-dosha. Wood→Fire is a plasma and EM description, essential to understanding the consumption of Aether (*A* power). In fact, the Fire trigram’s proper name is The Clinging 離, which signifies the tendency of the plasma to need fuel and to ‘cling’ to wood. More to the point, the Law of Conservation - via the Thermodynamic subset - stipulates that fire must have a fuel. Therefore the *A* power, arising out of Water, - provides the upper gradient, while “wood” flows downward in gradient²⁰ (hence curl) into the *use of* EM. This passes, if one reviews the MIMS documents²¹ and

¹⁹ The author could easily justify 2 or 3 other arrangements

²⁰ Hence the Earth is full of potential and the rules of potential control gradients, not LRC. The LRC stores potential and uses it.

²¹ https://www.academia.edu/86538573/MIMS_2_21_The_Union_of_the_5_and_8

diagrammatica²², through the above lying region of the Law of Polarity *and the Law of Resonance* back to the Fire-aligned (PEMF, *L* power, *k* region, etc.) Law of Causation, where expression is manifest. It is seen in *actualization*, and in the LRC behaviors of the circuit - be it light, electronics, solar system, HEGEME²³, etc. The subtle issue here is the facts of life-cycles, be they of the stars or Earth, or of carbon-based lifeforms. They appear to falling into a pattern of waxing and waning, which causes either the mind to observe the Law of Rotation's interaction with the Law of Evolution (causing Change) - the other axis of the "X" in bagua dharma - or the actual facts of empirical, cyclic change. The author maintains it is an "as above, so below" type situation: because the Changes are **real**, the unduped mind can see them and after eliminating the dukkha (suppressed or deluded ignorant mind leading to suffering) the person will also have a sense of the Changes as real. This was the long process of realization that Liu Yiming got not only from the Wuzhu Pian, and studied on it, but of the Changes in the "I Ching", until he wrote in the Taoist I Ching - one of mankind's' greatest mimical treasures,

"all my doubts disappeared, so that for the first time I realized that the Tao of spiritual alchemy is none other than the Tao of the I Ching, the Tao of sages is none other than the Tao of immortals, and that the I Ching is not a book of divination but rather is the study of investigation of principles, fulfillment of nature, and arrival at the meaning of life."

Please bear in mind the bagua-taijitu, and therefore the diagrammatica of the I Ching was based on Perattian synchrotron formations - toroids - and seen worldwide as an "8 spoked wheel". This has been covered rote elsewhere in the EPEMC literature²⁴.

Conclusionary Speculation

Rather than a firm conclusion the author would like to suggest that deep dives into these three items, with ORDAINED²⁵ quantizations, and dætherical²⁶ or fibonacci analysis²⁷, looking for pressure waves, nodal points, and asymmetry²⁸, will lead an analyst or natural philosopher/scientist to discover more on this issue.

1. The Dougherty Set of diagrams related to Hopf Vibrations, et al.
2. The Change Theory as it relates not only to Cosmic Rearrangement Hypothesis but the proposed (elsewhere) Aether Flexion Wave
3. The MIMSical "gravity project" - aka the General Relativity Fixer-Upper - looking into the diagrammatica of gravity²⁹, as well as replacing the Newtonian equation with PEMF versions for the PEMC.
 - a. $Kg \rightarrow KeV \rightarrow j$ (full ME conversion)
 - b. $G \rightarrow k\text{-Gurvature}$ ³⁰ ?

²²

https://www.academia.edu/87365333/MESS0003_MIMS_2_21_1_the_Literal_Union_of_the_5_and_8_a_pre_MIMS_Diagrammatica_Explained

²³

https://www.academia.edu/36753643/Our_Plasma_Electromagnetic_Sky_Application_of_Hollow_Expanding_Growing_Electromagnetic_Earth_Hypothesis_with_particular_respect_to_the_Earths_Atmosphere_starting_from_the_Lithosphere_and_ascending_Altitude

²⁴ <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc>

²⁵ https://www.academia.edu/87578071/MESS0007_MIMS_2_101_The_ORDA_Standard

²⁶ https://www.academia.edu/67236577/MIMS_2_102_In_pursuit_of_the_Daether

²⁷ https://www.academia.edu/67387410/MIMS_2_1_212a_Fibonacci_Pressure

²⁸ [The Keys of Asymmetry & Successes of EPEMC](#)

²⁹ [MESS0014: CRH - Gravity as Resonance and Conservation](#)

³⁰ A proposed Gaussian curvature expression of Curl and Gradient

The author has no firm assertions or conclusions about any of the topics discussed above, except to point out that there is a definite need for more funding on Change Theory, beyond meteorology and stocks/market analysis, to define chaotivity and fractalicity in a quantized/numericalized approach. Only in this way can the Value fields be defined, and a dætheric expression or ORDA project finds firm the secrets of the “Dao” of the Changes. In determining how this produces the effects which decay or destroy families, communities, societies, cultures, nations, and empires - that controls future History - we must apply great expenses of mimsical energy, time, and computerized analysis. For the sake not of globalist or corporate power, but the creation of forward societies. Of Tesla’s edict: increasing Human Momentum³¹.

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